

Outcomes of the Cross-border Stakeholder's Workshop

Spain and Portugal – IEO & UAVR

Galicia Bank-Vigo and Vasco da Gama Seamounts - *Case study workshop*

- **Place and date:** Vigo (Spain), - November 28th 2018.
- **Organizers:** Spanish Institute of Oceanography (IEO), the University of Aveiro (UAVR), the Center for Experimental Studies and Public Works (CEDEX) and the Technological Center of the Sea (CETMAR)
- **Language:** Portuguese and Spanish
- **Participants:** 32 stakeholders from both countries clustered around 6 sectors with potential interests in the study area:
 - (1) Conservation
 - (2) Marine Research
 - (3) Fisheries
 - (4) Navigation
 - (5) Energy and Mineral Resources and
 - (6) Renewable Energies

Methodology

The workshop was held in a unique day session divided in 4 parts:

- I. **Plenary talks**: Presentations by coordinators from the project and the representatives of MSP authorities from the two countries.
- II. **Exercise 1**: Organised in four round-tables were set up with 2 participants from 2 sectors (+ research and conservation) focused in identifying :
 - a) Synergies
 - b) Conflicts
 - c) Gapsbetween uses that might arise in the area.

Participants had their activities (fisheries, renewal energies, etc.) mapped on paper and transparencies, which allowed them to make notes and draw on the maps, as well as overlay the information of different sectors.

- I. **Exercise 2**: Find solutions for the identified conflicts.
- I. **Plenary session**: Summarize and unify main conclusions.

Materials

- Factsheets of maritime sectors in different sizes printed in paper and transparencies:

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Apoyo a la implementación de la Ordenación Espacial Marina en el Atlántico Norte

CONSERVACIÓN E INVESTIGACIÓN

COMENTARIOS

OTROS STAKEHOLDERS

Mapa de la zona de estudio y valores naturales.

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VALORES NATURALES

COMENTARIOS

OTROS STAKEHOLDERS

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PESCA MARITIMA

COMENTARIOS

OTROS STAKEHOLDERS

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ENERGÍA SUBMARINA

COMENTARIOS

OTROS STAKEHOLDERS

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ENERGÍAS RENOVABLES

COMENTARIOS

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CONTEXTO GENERAL SIMNORAT Y ÁREA DE ESTUDIO

COMENTARIOS

OTROS STAKEHOLDERS

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Main conclusions: Synergies and Conflicts

Main conclusions: Gaps

Main conclusions: Solutions

thank you | merci | gracias | obrigada